

ENABLING INNOVATION IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT TO ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

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ABSTRACT: To ensure sustainable development, there is a limit to the extent of urbanization. Thus, rural development is an essential strategy that many nations must work on to ensure optimal economic, environmental, and social outcomes at a country level. However, rural development in itself is challenging because rural communities typically have limited resources and capabilities to address common livelihood challenges, let alone take on new economic roles. Hence, as part of rural revitalization strategies, innovation plays a critical role. A wide range of technologies can facilitate innovation in rural development, including the internet and new agricultural technologies. In addition, new mindsets and shifts in values, such as the changing trends of work and consumerism, can create opportunities for rural areas to adopt innovation and develop new growth engines. However, it should be noted that the nature of innovation in rural and urban settings are different. In rural regions, growth could be enabled through more specific types of innovations, including frugal innovation, inclusive innovation, and social innovation. To enable these forms of innovations in rural areas, this paper proposes a three-dimensional process model that includes pro-social technological innovation policy, rural innovation governance, and dynamic networks that close the gap between rural and urban innovation systems. Examples from China, such as the development of Tengtou Village and Taobao Villages serve to demonstrate these concepts. Overall, the discussions in the paper suggest that to enable innovation in rural development, it is necessary to foster closer interactions between rural and urban innovation ecosystems for the former to leverage the latter's technologies, networks, and resources.

KEY WORDS: Rural Development, Sustainable Development Goals, Innovation, Development Policy

1. INTRODUCTION

To achieve sustainable development, it is paramount for the current generation to utilize resources wisely without compromising future generations' needs. To this end, it is arguable that the extent of urbanization in every country must be well-calibrated to prevent urban centers from over-consuming a nation's limited resources, which could be detrimental to the economic, environmental, and social outcomes of rural regions. Hence, most nations need to work on rural development because excessive urbanization is not sustainable. For instance, it would not be tenable to have incessant rural-urban immigration flows because urban centers may not have sufficient resources and job opportunities to support massive immigrant population growth.

Consequently, many rural areas have been compelled to adopt new economic responsibilities. It is challenging for rural regions to take on these additional roles while grappling with existing constraints, such as the lack of affordable technologies to address basic needs like sanitary water. The added responsibilities also mean rural areas have to navigate the complexities and competitive dynamics of global trading.

In this light, innovation in rural development could play a critical role in supporting economic development, mitigating social disparity, and reducing environmental impact. Technology innovation in rural development can tap on global trends, including growing globalization, enhanced communications technologies, and shorter geographic distances due to better transportation. Place-based innovation could also support rural development. Nevertheless, there are various factors that affect the willingness and ability to innovate, such as literacy rates,

availability of resources, access to technology, and conduciveness of policies.

The nature of innovation in urban and rural areas can differ greatly. For instance, larger towns with universities and businesses are usually big enough to have formal research and development networks and innovation ecosystems. In contrast, although rural areas may not have the economies of scale, they can still utilize technologies to integrate efforts across multiple communities and create significant research and development synergies. Furthermore, science-based initiatives in metropolitan areas, like bioenergy research centered in forests, can have applications in rural areas too (Tharian, 2023).

Figure 1 presents a potential framework to illustrate how various emerging technologies and trends could translate into drivers of rural innovation: since agriculture is often the primary economic activity in rural areas, innovations in agriculture technologies and decentralized power supply would be pertinent. New advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics, that have brought massive efficiency increases in urban centers, might also be applicable as industrial activities, such as manufacturing, start relocating to rural areas. Furthermore, Internet-of-Things (IoT) and cloud computing solutions will be essential to enable advanced communications and efficient coordination in rural areas that could create value for economic activities. In addition, as rural areas are typically less densely populated compared to urban areas, driverless cars and drones could also provide offer more efficient and low-carbon transportation alternatives. Another notable gamechanger is the shifting of values within rural environments that may significantly affect innovation patterns, and encourage new technologies. For example, growing emphasis on the quality of health and access to

education could create considerable demand for relevant technology innovations on these fronts. The rise of the “work-from-home” phenomenon due to the recent COVID-19 pandemic also suggests that advances in internet technologies could transform the future of work, which might have implications on the economic activities in rural areas too. This paper shall discuss how some of these potential drivers enable innovation and development in rural areas.

environmental degradation and the disparity between urban and rural growth also highlight the urgency for governance reform and innovation for rural development.

In particular, although China has made great strides to be one of the global leaders in science and technology innovation, including quantum communications, aerospace engineering, satellite, artificial intelligence, and other fields, it lagged behind other countries in innovation related to the well-being of people, such as the agricultural and food processing industry, furniture manufacturing industry, and textile and apparel industry. For instance, China was investing in agricultural science and technology at a rate of only 0.3% of the value of all agricultural produce, compared to Israel at 3% (Gulati et al., 2021). In fact, Israel's advancements in science and technology were responsible for 96% of the increase in agricultural output in the 1980s (Gulati et al., 2021).

In response, in October 2017, the Communist Party of China National Congress formally proposed the implementation of rural revitalization strategy. Subsequently, Chinese government agencies went on to develop a set of policies that outlined the direction for rural regeneration (Mulholland, 2018). The plan underlined that in order to resolve the conflicts between people's rising aspirations for a better living and uneven growth, attaining innovation-driven development must come first. Additionally, it is essential for encouraging sustainable development and international peace as well as the goal of creating universal riches by the year 2050 (Baker, 2015). As China has grown to become one of the world's global superpowers, this major move signals that rural revitalization could become a strategy to work towards sustainable development for more countries in future.

3. THE NATURE OF INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

Innovation can play an important role in rural development. A scan of the current literature on innovation for rural development suggests most current innovation efforts focus on the agriculture aspects. Besides academia, corporates also seem to see value in agricultural innovation in rural development. For instance, agricultural biotechnology firm, Monsanto, previously implemented a Smallholder Program to provide technological support to smallholder farmers in some developing countries where Monsanto had businesses (Glover, 2007).

Such a focus on innovation for agriculture uses is not unexpected since rural areas typically have a sizable smallholder farmer community. Moreover, the emergence of challenges to conventional farming models, such as the lack of manpower due to the rural exodus and environmental threats like desertification, means that innovative agricultural solutions are often top-of-mind when discussing innovation in rural areas (Ocolisanu et al., 2022).

However, innovation in rural areas should not be limited to agricultural applications. There are increasing innovations related to the demands for sustainable development. Mitticool, for instance, is an example of an entrepreneurial venture in India arising from efforts to bring affordable products, such as clay fridges, to sustain livelihood in poor communities (Hossain et al., 2023). The fact that rural communities are finding new solutions that did not exist only one generation ago and innovations that mirror the changes that our society is currently undergoing is not by chance. Rural dwellers are increasingly looking for better products, high-quality services, and new social connections that the rural setting can provide. There are also new

Figure 1. Key drivers for rural change

2. THE ROLE OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The United Nations (UN) established seventeen sustainable development goals (SDGs) in 2015. These goals are meant to reduce disparity between communities and help to improve the management and distribution of resources critical to livelihood, such as air, water, energy and food. However, according to recent reports by the UN, the world is lagging behind targets to meet the targets of the SDGs (UN, 2020). This shortfall could be due to trends that exacerbate the very issues that the SDGs seek to address.

Take urbanization. Urbanization is a global trend, and the percentage of people living in urban areas increased from 33% in 1960 to 55% in 2017 (Ritchie and Roser, 2018). The widening rural-urban divide and the accompanying rural decline – which could have serious negative effects on global sustainable development, such as poverty, subpar land management, inadequate education, underdeveloped infrastructure conditions, and even crime – are worrying global issues. These current problems necessitate urgent rural revitalization initiatives that will promote sustainable rural development alongside urbanization as both villages and city inhabitants should enjoy resources, public services, and social welfare on an equitable basis (Ramlee et al., 2015).

China serves as an example of a country trying to balance rural development with urbanization to achieve sustainable development. On the one hand, its unprecedented urbanization rates seemed to have alleviated poverty effectively: China's urbanization rate increased from 19% in 1980 to 57% in 2016 (The World Bank, 2018), while poverty decreased from almost 90% in 1980 to 4% in 2016 (Ravallion, 2021). On the other hand, China's non-competitive agriculture sector, slow rural growth, and farmers' poor income, underscore the need for comprehensive rural revitalization. Additionally, issues like

demands arising from the needs to maintain the standard of rural areas and preserve natural resources.

Furthermore, the diversification of local economies and the deepening of interactions between local and global ecosystems lead to the creation of new synergies. These trends and forces in rural areas can shape and influence innovation in rural settings.

3.1. The need for innovation for rural development

Schumpeter's new growth theory offers a useful perspective to approach innovation. The theory contends that innovation and the information it produces are the foundation of the knowledge economy and the primary forces behind long-term economic growth (Aghion et al., 2015). Furthermore, according to Arrow (1972), information, a crucial type of knowledge product created by invention and creativity, develops into a significant, immutable good with economic worth for the welfare growth of economics (Arrow, 1972). Romer (1986) also added that under the new long-run growth model, where knowledge is an input in production with growing marginal productivity, growth rate could increase over time, in contrast to the old growth model that forecasted decreasing returns (Romer, 1986). In particular, endogenous technological changes may improve the competitive equilibrium by incorporating information created by technological innovation into economic development models.

Accordingly, Schumpeter advanced a new growth model that was motivated by technical advancement brought on by deliberate investment choices made by profit-seekers. Per the new growth hypothesis, growth cannot be produced by a big population if there is insufficient human capital invested in the advancement of science and technology. Hence, based on the new growth theory, shifting rural development away from the longstanding labor-intensive and low-tech traditions, and moving toward the new growth models driven by science and technology innovation, is the key to achieving rural revitalization.

3.2. Local economy diversification

There are several new opportunities for economic diversification and innovation in rural areas. New needs in services are emerging for the rural population, which may be met by small units of production. Furthermore, as rural communities get uplifted from poverty, their demand for quality products rise correspondingly, and may present opportunities for small-scale production, which are primarily focused on economies of scope rather than on economies of scale.

In a similar situation, new roles for the rural sector are emerging in resource management and environmental protection. For example, a growing environmental awareness is associated with the return to extensive farming in less productive areas. In line with the SDGs, there is also a strong desire to preserve the countryside and cultural heritage to foster a better balance between agriculture and the environment, as well as a diversification of farmers' roles and the development of new communities. Finally, the precariousness of markets and jobs also encourages diversification strategies, both at the local level and at the national level.

3.3. Local and global context differences and synergies

A number of rural areas were still relatively isolated until the 1970s. Today, a number of factors are promoting an increased opening to the outside world, such as the drivers illustrated in Figure 1. For example, with a shift in values, the establishment

of the European Union and the strengthening of the Single Market have ended the isolation experienced by certain regions in Europe. Furthermore, large-scale infrastructure projects built throughout Europe in the 1970s and 1980s have made the countryside more accessible and easier to travel to. Additionally, modern information and communication technologies are having a major influence on relationships. The rapid growth of information systems, which is linked to these technologies, is another factor that helps to strengthen rural regions' relationships with the urban world by allowing distances and modes of transportation to be transcended. Databanks provide the information required by even the most isolated rural enterprises, enabling them to segment their products and sales systems in accordance with precisely-targeted markets. At the same time, the prevalence of teleworking is growing, providing new opportunities to rural society; businesses looking for space and lower rent could even potentially relocate to rural areas by the reduction in space-time made possible by these technologies.

These examples suggest that a potential strategy in fostering innovation in rural development could involve leveraging innovation networks in nearby urban centers to co-create synergies. The question that is currently being asked focuses particularly on understanding how to manage the connections between the rural and urban world. While each rural area is now able to leave its isolation and access information beneficial for its development, it still needs to be aware of how to make wise decisions, form the most crucial connections, and establish open and transparent partnership relations.

3.4. Systemic challenges to innovation in rural settings

Rural revitalization also depends on institutional and management arrangements to foster engagements to achieve the social mission of rural revitalization while generating economic profit through technological innovation, especially since innovation is often regarded as a risky social interaction learning process.

Moreover, higher environmental and cultural barriers to knowledge creation and diffusion in rural areas include an underdeveloped knowledge and information transaction market, a lack of generalized social trust for risk-taking, more short-term oriented behaviors, and poverty. These aspects of rural life may be detrimental to entrepreneurship and innovation. Thus, institutional reforms that encourage involvement of various agents, such as alternative organizational forms, including public sector or other non-profit organizations, as well as individual talents, are necessary. To cite an example of these new types of organizational forms, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) has established ninety-two Accelerator Labs across 116 countries to provide structured training for developing innovations to address real-life problems (UNDP, 2020).

Despite the clear demand and ongoing efforts on the ground, innovation for rural development has received relatively little attention in the innovation literature, especially outside the realm of agriculture. This gap demands for the introduction of a systematic viewpoint to comprehend and create rural innovation systems. Investigating how rural innovation networks, intermediates, and platforms affect rural innovation will undoubtedly add to both the new growth theory and the innovation system theory, which will ultimately speed up rural revitalization plans.

3.5. Innovation paradigms in rural setting

Recent innovation paradigms relevant to rural setting include social innovation, frugal innovation, responsible innovation, inclusive innovation, and holistic innovation. These paradigms all place an emphasis on the social responsibility of achieving balanced development between rural and urban areas and offer helpful insights on how to build rural innovation systems.

For instance, when it comes to the creation and use of fresh concepts to satisfy social demands and enhance the quality of life, social innovation experts criticize the narrow-mindedness of commercial innovation. The methods and research in social innovation have the power to change public management, business strategy, and innovation systems.

Frugal innovation, on the other hand, offers suggestions on how to run businesses to benefit low-income areas and their residents while still generating a profit. The topic was first brought up in the context of developing nations, like India, where solutions to the demands of customers who are cost-conscious were sought. Frugal innovation is a process that encourages people living in resource-constrained conditions to think more deeply about the challenges they face and use innovation to commercialize potential solutions; doing so also helps to create value to alleviate poverty and uplift livelihoods (Zeschky et al., 2014).

While emphasizing the inclusion of innovation for low-income earners and the poor rather than merely for the rich and developed market, inclusive innovation works in accordance with the philosophy of inclusive development. In addition to bringing new technology and commercial prospects to rural communities, inclusive innovation is helpful in fostering social entrepreneurship. One noteworthy example is inclusive innovation-driven microfinance, which supports rural and low-income areas for community development.

Holistic innovation is a new paradigm that advocates embracing holistic thinking at the corporate and societal levels as a way to address the dichotomy between short-term and long-term behaviors. In order to achieve a balanced development, this paradigm places a specific emphasis on the creation of sustainable ecosystems that can encourage cooperation between rural and urban innovation systems.

4. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN RURAL AREAS

Rural innovation system's ecological growth and value generation could be sped up by leveraging the innovation and technology transferred from urban innovation system. In particular, interactions between the rural and urban ecosystems could help to better transmit and apply business models and technologies, such as those reflected in Figure 1, from urban areas to rural settings. The linkage between rural urban innovation system can be achieved through intermediaries and networks like the internet

The rural innovation system can also aid in the development of rural infrastructure, relevant financial systems, and conducive cultural climate by re-evaluating innovation policies and maximizing the portfolio of innovation resources. Additionally, it will speed up the process of policy decision-making and diffusion, foster rural entrepreneurship, encourage the use of new knowledge in rural innovation systems, raise the percentage of science and technology contribution to rural development, and ultimately lead to the sustainable development in rural areas.

In other words, innovation is seldom the result of a single technological or factor input action, but rather a multi-step process of building systems, networks, policies, and scientific knowledge. Yet, the local collective economy in rural areas, usually comprising farmer and small-medium enterprises, are often constrained in terms of scale, money, and managerial know-how, making them far less capable of technology innovation than the businesses in the metropolitan system. Thus, rural revitalization policies must be comprehensive to foster rural innovation through technological innovations. Rural innovation systems do not have access to technological centers, such as universities and research institutes, like urban innovation systems do. Therefore, rural innovation system must work with urban innovation system in addition to enhancing the investment of technology and the cultivation of other innovation skills.

Furthermore, the establishment and improvement of a government-led science and technology innovation system should not be the only factors influencing rural innovation capacity. Rural governance must also support rural innovation by reforming urbanization, land management, and collective property rights. An essential assurance for the transformation of the rural governance system is management innovation based on institutional reforms. In order to reduce poverty and promote inclusive growth in rural areas, it is crucial for local self-governing organizations and township- or village-owned businesses to attract full-time and full-participation innovation. Specific to the agricultural context, it will be easier to retain rural workers, attract more innovative talents, and effectively use big data, e-commerce, and rural e-government tools to improve rural governance if specialized agricultural services are encouraged and agricultural management systems are built faster.

A case in point is the Tengtou Village in China. In the 1980s, farmers left the village in search of better employment in cities. Large tracts of land were thus abandoned. The village's committee head at the time, Fu Qiping, proposed proposals for land management reform and guided the people in putting those reforms into effect. Then, Tengtou Village successfully carried out the building of ecological agriculture activities, reform of the collective business shareholding structure, and transformation plan of the ancient village. Tengtou Village eventually won the United Nations "Global 500 Awards for Environmental Achievements" and went on to become one of the first groups of national civilized villages, national ecological demonstration areas, and national 5A-class tourist attractions. This was made possible by the quick development of a rural innovation system. The rural governance structure was continuously improved, which enabled Tengtou Village to construct the "Tengtou Ecosystem" eco-innovation development model, achieve rural prosperity, and promote sustainable development (Gong, 2010).

Today, the difference in development between rural and urban regions is more obvious. In general, entrepreneurial challenges in rural locations include a lack of funding for micro and small businesses, the lack of experience of untrained entrepreneurs, and unsustainable business models. The growth of rural entrepreneurs is threatened by less affluent and rural regions, which usually lack an entrepreneurial climate and have a small consumer base. In order to support rural entrepreneurs, public intermediaries could interconnect rural regions by creating rural and regional innovation networks.

Entrepreneurial activity makes a substantial contribution to economic expansion in rural areas. The role of entrepreneurship in addressing the SDGs is growing and may constantly evolve. Since entrepreneurship fosters economic activity, it is crucial for

rural development; the notion of rural entrepreneurship places a strong emphasis on how innovation helps rural communities create economic value.

The speed of rural innovation capacity improvement is determined by the open movement and application of knowledge, talents, money, and new technologies within the system. Therefore, creating an open community that will increase network organization ability, speed up the free flow of inventive components, and support the effective transformation of new technology is key to fostering rural innovation capacity and expediting rural revitalization. The value creation and distribution in the rural innovation system will be transformed during this process by community-based networks and intermediaries like new kinds of agricultural cooperatives, inclusive financial systems, agricultural technology remote training systems, information support systems, and contemporary logistics systems.

The enhancement of the rural innovation network infrastructure and the connection between the innovation system and the urban innovation system are particularly benefited by the growth of the modern internet and modern logistics. This will link urban and rural innovation factors and economic possibilities, accelerating the flow of human capital and intellectual capital in both urban and rural locations. These linkages significantly contribute to lowering transaction costs in rural areas and between rural and urban networks.

The Alibaba Rural Strategy is a good illustration of how the internet, new business models, and entrepreneurship can boost the development of rural networks and rejuvenate rural areas. Alibaba, a large e-commerce company in China, introduced the plan in late 2014, enabling rural inhabitants to do online transactions for the purchase and sale of goods on Taobao, the company's online marketplace. Since then, rural Taobao networks have continuously grown since its launch, now covering over 30,000 villages and 700 counties across China's 29 provinces. To enable e-commerce distribution in rural areas, the business established hundreds of service centers. Some "Taobao Villages," which are connected to the global online market through the Taobao platform, eventually gained shape as the rural logistics infrastructure improved.

About 2,100 Taobao Villages existed at the end of 2017, and the e-commerce sector had generated more than 28 million job opportunities in China by then, with more than RMB 120 billion in total sales. By using the Taobao Village in Lishui, Zhejiang Province, as an example, farmers can learn from one another through community demonstrations, social demonstrations, and a network business association platform. This encouraged rural farmers to become more entrepreneurial and attracted a collection of logistics and other supporting service providers, which in turn fostered the growth of rural e-commerce (Leong et al., 2016).

This case study also shows that in the big data era, it is also possible to encourage the growth of rural innovation networks, create urban-rural synergy, and accomplish poverty alleviation and rural development through network and intermediate platform innovation. As a result of information technology and e-commerce, virtual communities like Taobao Village provide new opportunities to improve the dynamics of networks connecting rural and urban communities for complementary growth. To close the gap between urban and rural innovation systems and promote a more balanced regional innovation system, more initiatives like this are required.

5. DISCUSSION

It is a long-term, systematic, and difficult process to build and leverage the rural innovation system in order to revitalize the countryside. The theoretical structural model must be applied to the development of a rural innovation system, and both policymakers and academics must identify the key issues and potential directions for further study. This paper suggests that fostering a robust and effective rural innovation system involves achieving a three-dimensional process model: pro-social technological innovation policy, rural innovation governance, and dynamic networks that close the gap between rural and urban innovation systems. Although these three components of the rural innovation system can work well together to support the development of the system and boost rural innovation capacity, establishing and leveraging the system to revitalize rural areas and achieve balanced and inclusive urban-rural development is a long-term, intricate process.

Furthermore, although the main force behind rural endogenous technological growth is innovation, the supply of resources and environments can rarely keep up with the demand. Thus, designing a pro-rural technological innovation policy is therefore of utmost importance in order to provide the foundation for rural revival. In fact, rural revitalization strategy is the embodiment of innovation-driven development strategy in rural areas in countries like China. Consequently, the top-level rural innovation policy should take into account both the logic of rural development and its challenges, in addition to adhering to the general innovation policy. The first step in rebalancing innovation policies that are skewed toward urban and metropolitan systems is to assess the current national and regional innovation policies.

New and distinct pro-rural technology innovation policy portfolios must be created in order to foster the spread of new technology and new business models into rural areas from metropolitan and even international locations. To achieve the simultaneous advancement of development, environmental protection, and rural indigenous innovation, the government should also increase public investment in rural technologies and quicken the implementation of policies and laws for high-tech development, for instance, in agriculture.

The assurance for bridging top-down and bottom-up activities for rural innovation is institutional frameworks. The success of the rural governance system is crucial to the development of institutional infrastructure. A change in the system of rural governance can strengthen the institutional framework for implementing pro-rural innovation policies and foster a cultural environment that aids in the development of relevant technologies, promotion of entrepreneurship, and attraction of new talent back to rural areas for innovation and entrepreneurship.

For instance, researchers and policymakers must determine what kind of new organizations are most effective in fostering innovation in agricultural science and technology, so that more young talents might take on farming jobs in rural areas. In order to improve rural innovation capabilities, it is also necessary to reconsider relevant legal frameworks. This includes reforming the rural land system and the property rights framework. Additionally, the career promotion process for government officers has to be improved in order to give public servants significant institutional incentives to implement the rural rehabilitation approach.

While networks and intermediate organizations offer several ways to speed up the exchange of information within the rural innovation system, improving coordination between the rural and urban innovation systems remains a significant problem. The relationship between the rural and urban innovation systems has to be strengthened, which calls for more dynamic networks and intermediaries. This would reduce the transaction costs and market barriers preventing resources and new knowledge from moving from the urban innovation system to the rural innovation system.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the idea of a rural innovation system and contrasted the similarities and differences between rural and urban innovation systems in light of current innovation trends and the SDGs. It then presented a framework of the driving forces for developing a rural innovation system and discussed the potential and challenges involved in creating a robust and effective rural innovation system.

The paper also directly advanced rural studies in four different ways. First, this paper brought together researchers who focus on rural revitalization and researchers who focus on innovation-driven development, adding more knowledge to rural revitalization and sustainability. It did this by introducing new growth theory, institutional theory, and innovation literatures into rural studies. Second, in order to address the rural decline, this study proposed a rural innovation system and its structural model to strengthen rural innovation capacity for sustained endogenous technological improvements.

Third, this paper pointed out that rural innovation system has typically received less attention. Both academics and decision-makers have seen the strength and significance of urban innovation systems that reflect city vibrancy and economic progress, but more attention is needed to fully realize their promise for rural revival. Fourth, countries working on rural development can gain fresh momentum in their fight against poverty and in strengthening their capacity for innovation by adopting a three-dimensional process model: pro-social technological innovation policy, rural innovation governance, and dynamic networks that close the gap between rural and urban innovation systems.

In essence, this paper has offered new perspectives on how the world's sustainable development efforts might benefit from innovation in rural development. To realize this concept, more research and ground work could be carried out to dovetail national innovation-driven strategies with rural revitalization plans, particularly by examining how to foster greater interaction between the rural and urban innovation ecosystems.

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